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Research Article

In-Silico Prediction of Zingerone as A Potential Therapeutic Agent for Autistic Symptoms Via the Ca^{2+} Signaling Pathway: A Molecular Docking and Molecular Simulation Approach

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ABSTRACT

Zingerone (ZNO), a phenolic compound, has been extensively studied for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-apoptotic properties. ZNO has been firmly studied against several neurological diseases, asserting its neuroprotective activity. Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neuro-developmental disorder characterised by difficulty in developing social interactions and communications, restricted and repetitive patterns, and intellectual disability. Our study aimed to evaluate the absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity (ADMET) profile of ZNO through the SwissADME tool. The ability to cross the blood-brain-barrier (BBB) was assessed using the LogBBB tool. The binding energy of ZNO with Ca^{2+} signalling proteins was analysed using Autodock Vina 1.1.2 and further validated through GROMACS simulation studies. ADMET studies revealed ZNO to have ideal lipophilicity (1.79) and water solubility ($1.55e-01$ mg/mL). The boiled egg graph predicted ZNO as a negative substrate for permeability glycoproteins (PGP-), overall indicating to have optimal bioavailability (55% oral). LogBBB analysis predicted ZNO to be BBB permeable (-0.16203). Molecular docking analysis revealed that ZNO-calmodulin kinase-II α subunit (-6.7kJ/mol) and ZNO-calmodulin kinase-IV (-6.3kJ/mol) had the highest binding affinity. The stability of the complexes was analysed in a 100ns simulation and found to be stable. Therefore, in the current study, for the first time, we report the possibility of ZNO to attenuate autistic symptoms through in-silico modelling via the Ca^{2+} signalling pathway.

INTRODUCTION

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a heterogeneous neuro-developmental disorder with

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symptoms that predominantly onset between 12 to 24 months of age. The peculiarity of ASD is known from an early developmental window, showing persistent difficulties in social interaction and communication, stereotypical, restricted and repetitive behavioural patterns, and varying degrees of intellectual disability^[1]. The disorder is accompanied by other prominent comorbidities that tend to cluster into different subgroups that manifest as impairments outside the core characteristics of ASD^[2]. The overlapping tendencies of the core symptoms and the comorbidities explain the heterogeneity aspects of ASD.

Several proteins and genes are considered high risk in autism. Dysfunction in proteins associated with the intracellular calcium (Ca^{2+}) signalling, such as parvalbumin (PVALB), a cytosolic Ca^{2+} buffering protein, resulted in enlarged cell body and mitochondrial size primarily in regions rich in PVALB⁺ neurons^[3]. *Pvalb*^{-/-} mice also exhibited three ASD-related core behavioural phenotypes, anomalous social reciprocity, communication impediment, and recurrent and stereotyped behaviour^[4]. An E183V mutation of the α subunit of calmodulin kinase II (CaMKII α) resulted in the dysregulation of dendritic morphology and synaptic transmission, ultimately causing robust ASD-like behavioural phenotypes in mice^[5]. Additionally, altered expression of calmodulin kinase IV (CAMKIV) and dysfunction in its surface activators, such as CaV1.2, mGluR1, and mGluR5, are shown to be associated with autism^[6]. Aberrant cognitive function and its associated behavioural abnormality were also associated with decreased brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) expression in autistic patients^[7]. The hypothesis on the involvement of intracellular calcium signalling in autistic individuals and in pre-clinical ASD models is relatively new, with fewer studies.

Zingerone (ZNO) is a phenolic compound derived from 6-gingerol by reverse aldolization reaction found in thermally labile ginger. Drying, roasting or cooking ginger has been shown to increase the amount of ZNO extensively^[8, 9]. ZNO has been comprehensively studied for its anti-oxidant^[10-13], anti-inflammatory^[10,11,13], and anti-apoptotic properties^[13-16]. Such a widely appreciated molecule with diverse pharmaceutical properties had yet to be studied for its possible effects against ASD-associated proteins. Based on the above-mentioned considerations, we found it plausible to critically investigate the adsorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion (ADMET) and bioavailability of ZNO. Further, to understand the binding ability of ZNO with ASD related pathway through molecular docking analysis. For the first time, we report the binding ability of ZNO towards ASD related proteins and further validate the complex through molecular dynamics analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Swiss ADME analysis

SwissADME is a computer web-based tool that assesses the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) of a potential therapeutic drug based on its in-house prolific methods such as the BOILED-Egg^[17], iLOGP^[18], and bioavailability radar^[19]. Briefly, the SMILES entry of ZNO^[20] was copied and pasted in the input box of SwissADME, and 'run' was clicked. The results obtained were then retrieved and interpreted^[19].

LogBBB analysis

LogBB_Pred is a machine learning web-based tool used to predict the blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability (logBB) value^[21]. The SMILES entry of ZNO retrieved from PubChem was directly copied and pasted into the 'INPUT SMILES' entry and submitted. A compound predicated to have a

logBB value less than or equal to -1 is considered 'BBB permeable'.

Molecular Docking analysis

Molecular docking and binding site analysis were conducted using Autodock vina 1.1.2^[22]. Briefly,

the 3D structure of ZNO was retrieved from PubChem. The crystal structures of the proteins were downloaded from AlphaFold Protein Structure Database^[23,24] based on their UniProt IDs (Table 1).

Table 1: Uniport IDs and binding cavities of the crystal structure of proteins

S. No.	Ligand - PubChem ID	Proteins	Proteins – UniPort ID	Binding Cavities	Source
1	Zingerone 31211	Brain-derived neurotrophic factor	P23363 BDNF_RAT	Chain A: LYS187 CYS188 ASN189 PRO190 TYR193 THR194 LYS195 GLU196 GLY197 CYS198 ASN207 SER208 GLN209 CYS210 ARG211 THR212 CYS239 THR244	Cavity predicted from CB DOCK 2
2		Parvalbumin	P02625 PRVA_RAT	D52 D54 S56 E63 D91 D93 D95 K97 E102	From UniPort
3		Calcineurin - Protein phosphatase 3 catalytic subunit- α	P63329 PP2BA_RAT	D90 H92 D118 N150 H151 H199 H281 W352	From UniPort
4		Calmodulin I	P0DP29 CALM1_RAT	D21 D23 D25 T27 E32 D57 D59 N61 T63 E68 D94 D96 N98 Y100 E105 D130 D132 D134 Q136 E141	From UniPort
5		Calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase type II subunit alpha	P11275 KCC2A_RAT	LGKGAFSVV 19 to 27, K42, D135	From UniPort
6		Calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase type IV	P13234 KCC4_RAT	LGRGATSIV 48-56, K71 D160	From Uniport
7		Voltage-dependent L-type calcium channel subunit alpha-1C	P22002 CAC1C_RAT	E393 E736 E1144	From UniPort
8		Calbindin	P07171 CALB1_RAT	D24 D26 S28 Y30 E35 D111 D113 S115 E122 D155 N157 D159 K161 E166 D199 D201 N203 Y205 E21	From UniPort
9		Cyclic AMP-responsive element-binding protein 1	P15337 CREB1_RAT	Chain A: THR163 SER165 GLY166 GLN167 LEU179 ASN181 ASN182 GLN188 GLY189 LEU190 GLN191 THR192 LEU193 ILE207	Cavity predicted from CB DOCK 2

				LEU208 GLN209 TYR210 ALA211 GLN212 GLN218	
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The ligand and proteins were prepared in AutoDockTools 1.5.7, from the Molecular Graphics Laboratory (MGL) tools suite^[25] based on standard protocols. The Grid box was set to the respective active cavities of the proteins identified from UniProt or detected from CB-Dock2^[26, 27]. The files were exported to the command prompt, and the Audock vina 1.1.2 directory was set. The binding affinity of each ligand-protein complex was obtained from the final log.txt file. The 2D and 3D images of the ligand-protein binding complexes were generated using Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer, 2025^[28] and PyMol 3.1^[29], respectively.

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations

MD simulations were carried out using GROMACS^[30], one of the most widely used tools in simulation studies for assessing the relative firmness and structural stability of biomolecules and their complexes^[31]. The AMBER ff99SB-ILDN force field was employed to generate the protein topology^[32], while the ligand topology was created using ACPYPE^[33]. The two topologies were combined to form the protein-ligand complex, which was used for further MD simulations. A dodecahedron periodic boundary condition was applied with a box dimension of 1.0nm^[30]. The simulation box was solvated using the TIP3P water model^[34]. To neutralise the system, 0.15 M NaCl was added. Energy minimisation (EM) was performed using the steepest descent algorithm^[30], followed by equilibration for 1ns each under NVT conditions (constant no. of particles, volume, and temperature at 300 K) and NPT conditions (constant no. of

particles, pressure at 1 bar, and temperature)^[30]. All simulation steps (EM, NVT, and NPT) utilised Molecular Dynamics Parameter files adapted from the protein-ligand MD simulation tutorial by Lemkul, 2024^[35]. The final production MD simulation was run for 100ns to analyse the stability of the protein-ligand complex. The root mean square deviation (RMSD), root mean square fluctuation (RMSF), radius of gyration (Rg), solvent accessibility surface area (SASA), hydrogen bond (H-bond), and molecular mechanics/Poisson-Boltzmann surface area analysis (MMPBSA) were analysed after MD using the previously described literature^[36].

RESULTS

In-silico SwissADME prediction of ZNO and BBB permeability analysis

SwissADME was utilised to understand the ADMET profile of ZNO as a potential drug candidate (Figure 1). The molecular weight of ZNO was 194.23g/mol, which lay in the optimal range of the Lipinski rule of five (MW < 500Da). The 'fraction Csp3' refers to the proportion of carbon atoms in a molecule that are sp³ hybridised. A fractional Csp3 value is expected to be at least 0.25. ZNO was reported to have a fractional Csp3 value of 0.36, considerably higher than the 0.25 suggested value. Molecular polar surface area (PSA) is a descriptor shown to correlate well with passive molecular transport through membranes, and therefore, allows prediction of transport properties of drugs. ZNO was reported to have a TPSA of 46.53Å, indicative of having optimal polar properties.

Figure 1: SwissADME analysis of ZNO

The partition coefficient between n-octanol (a lipid-like solvent) and water ($\log P_{o/w}$) is the classical descriptor for lipophilicity. The consensus $\log P_{o/w}$ value represents the arithmetic mean of the values predicted by five proposed methods (XLOGP3, WLOGP, MLOGP, SILICOS-IT, and iLOGP). The consensus $\log P_{o/w}$ value is typically reported within the range of -0.7 to +6.0. ZNO has a consensus $\log p_{o/w}$ value of 1.79, indicative of good lipophilicity.

Water solubility in SWISS ADME is predicted through several models such as the ESOL model, Ali model and SILICOS-IT model. All predicted values are the decimal logarithm of the molar solubility in water (Log S). All models predicted ZNO to be 'soluble' with a solubility score of 1.55e-01 mg/mL. The saturation graph of ZNO was in accordance with the above results obtained (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Saturation graph of ZNO in SwissADME

To evaluate the individual ADME behaviour of drugs, Swiss-ADME has models used to predict drug pharmacokinetics. The skin permeability score of ZNO was -6.70 cm/s, predictive of less skin permeability. This could mean that ZNO, when administered through the percutaneous route, may not be absorbed optimally, resulting in a low concentration in the bloodstream and at the site of action.

The predictions for passive human gastrointestinal absorption (HIA) and BBB permeation can both be assessed based on the Boiled egg model (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Boil-egg model of ZNO from SwissADME analysis

The pharmacokinetic profile in SwissADME also includes information about the interaction of drug candidates with cytochromes P450 (CYP). Depending on the type of study, 50% to 90% of the therapeutic molecules are substrate to any one of the five major isoforms of the CYP: CYP1A2, CYP2C19, CYP2C9, CYP2D6, CYP3A4. Inhibition of these isoenzymes is certainly a major indication of drug-drug interactions, leading to toxicity and other adverse effects. ZNO was reported to be PGP-, meaning it is a non-substrate of permeability glycoproteins, and is also not a substrate (non-inhibitor) for CYP2C19, CYP2C9, CYP2D6, and CYP3A4 isoenzymes involved in the metabolism of the drug. Contrarily, ZNO was reported as an inhibitor of CYP1A2. [CYP1A2](#) is a

The model is based on the drug acting as a substrate or a non-substrate of permeability glycoproteins (PGP). One of the major roles of PGP is to protect the brain from xenobiotics. From the boiled egg graphics, it can be visually noted that ZNO was predicted to be present inside the yolk (yellow), and indicated as PGP-. This could mean that ZNO is a non-substrate of PGP, signifying the drug may not be flushed out of the brain membrane rapidly, predicting the possible ability of ZNO to cross the BBB and reach the targeted site without inhibition.

member of the CYP1 family and is mainly expressed in the liver. It accounts for about 10% to 15% of the total [CYP](#) content of human liver and is responsible for the metabolism of 10% to 15% of drugs that undergo metabolism. This could mean that ZNO was predicted to be poorly eliminated from the body; however, there is no quantified data available on the level of CYP1A2 inhibition by ZNO in Swiss ADME.

Drug-likeness was established from structural or physiochemical inspections of compounds advanced enough to be considered oral-drug candidates. The Swiss ADME uses 5 rules for its assessment to consider a compound drug like the Lipinski (Pfizer) filter, the Ghose (Amgen), Veber

(GSK), Egan (Pharmacia), and Muegge (Bayer) methods. The Abbot bioavailability score is similar but seeks to predict the probability of a compound to have at least 10% oral bioavailability in rats or measurable Caco-2 permeability. Based on the Abbot bioavailability score, ZNO was predicted to have 55% oral bioavailability.

LogBB_Pred was used to predict the BBB permeability (logBB value) of ZNO. Generally, compounds with a predicted logBB over the cutoff of -1.0 are categorised as BBB-permeable. ZNO was expected to have a LogBB value of -0.16203 and was considered BBB permeable (Figure 4).

Result page displays query compound structures, predicted logBB values. 'BBB Permeable' or 'BBB Non-Permeable' is determined by the cutoff of logBB value. 'BBB Permeable' is $\text{LogBB} \geq -1$.

SMILES	2D depiction	LogBB value	BBB Permeability
<chem>CC(=O)CCC1=CC(=C(C=C1)O)OC</chem>		-0.16203	BBB Permeable

Figure 4: Log BB score of ZNO, indicating BBB permeability

Molecular docking of ZNO and ASD-related protein targets

The ligand ZNO was docked with Ca^{2+} signalling protein targets associated with ASD. The binding affinity of all ligand-protein complexes was expressed as kcal/mol (Table 2).

Table 2: Binding energies of the ZNO-protein complexes

S.No.	Ligand - PubChem ID	Proteins – UniPort ID	Binding Energy
1	Zingerone (31211)	P23363 BDNF RAT	- 5.3kcal/mol
2		P02625 PRVA RAT	- 4.3kcal/mol
3		P63329 PP2BA RAT	- 5.4kcal/mol
4		P0DP29 CALM1 RAT	- 4.9kcal/mol

5		P11275 KCC2A RAT	- 6.7kcal/mol
6		P13234 KCC4 RAT	- 6.3kcal/mol
7		P22002 CAC1C RAT	- 6.0kcal/mol
8		P07171 CALB1 RAT	- 5.1kcal/mol
9		P15337 CREB1 RAT	- 4.7kcal/mol

The ligand-protein complex of ZNO-BDNF (Figure 5) had a binding energy score of - 5.3kcal/mol. The complex was stabilised by ASN (A: 189), forming a carbon-hydrogen bond, a form of weak interaction, and further stabilised by pi-pi stacking between the aromatic rings of ZNO and TYR (A: 193).

Figure 5: a) represents the 2D image of ZNO-BDNF complex visualised using Biovia Discovery Studio, version 2025, and b) represents the 3D image of ZNO-BDNF complex visualised using PyMol, 3.1

The ligand-protein complex of ZNO-PRVA (Figure 6) had a binding energy score of -4.3kcal/mol, stabilised by conventional H-bonds

formed with THR (A: 105) and GLU (A: 101, 102), and pi-alkyl stacking with LYS (A: 92).

Figure 6: a) represents the 2D image of ZNO-PRVA complex visualised using Biovia Discovery Studio, version 2025, and b) represents the 3D image of ZNO-PRVA complex visualised using PyMol, 3.1

The ZNO-PP2BA (Figure 7) complex binding energy score was -5.4kcal/mol. The complex was stabilised by a conventional carbon-hydrogen bond with GLU (A: 481) and a pi-cation

interaction between the electron-rich, positively charged cationic LYS (A: 474) and the electron-rich pi system of the aromatic ring of ZNO, along with pi-alkyl interactions.

Figure 7: a) represents 2D image of the ZNO-PP2BA complex visualised using Biovia Discovery Studio, version 2025, and B) represents the 3D image of ZNO-PP2BA complex visualised using PyMol, 3.1

The ZNO-CALMI (Figure 8) complex binding energy score was -4.9kcal/mol. The ligand-protein complex was stabilised by conventional H-bonds

with ARG (A: 87) and pi-anion interaction with ASP (A: 94).

Figure 8: a) represents the 2D image of the ZNO-CALM1 complex visualised using Biovia Discovery Studio, version 2025, and b) represents the 3D image of the ZNO-CALM1 complex visualised using PyMol, 3.1

The ligand-protein complex of ZNO-KCC2A (Figure 9) had the highest binding energy score with -6.7kcal/mol. The complex was stabilised by pi-pi stacking between the pi electrons of the aromatic ring of PHE (A: 89) and the pi electrons

of the aromatic ring of ZNO. Other conventional H-bonds, carbon-hydrogen bonds, and pi-alkyl bonds further reinforced the overall stability of the complex.

Figure 9: a) represents the 2D image of the ZNO-KCC2A complex visualised using Biovia Discovery Studio, version 2025 and B) represents the 3D image of the ZNO-KCC2A complex visualised using PyMol, 3.1

The ligand-protein complex ZNO-KCC4 (Figure 10) had a binding energy score of -6.3kcal/mol. The pi-cation and pi-anion interactions, pi-sigma interaction with PHE (A: 234), and the pi-alkyl

interaction with LYS (A: 312) and TYR (A: 238) overall aided in the stabilisation of the ligand-protein complex.

Figure 10: a) represents the 2D image of ZNO-KCC4 complex visualised using Biovia Discovery Studio, version 2025, and b) represents the 3D image of the ZNO-KCC4 complex visualised using PyMol, 3.1

The ZNO-CACIC (Figure 11) complex had a binding energy score of -6.0kcal/mol. Conventional H-bonding with ASN (A: 1188) and

pi-alkyl interactions aided in the stabilisation of the complex.

Figure 11: a) represents the 2D image of the ZNO-CAC1C complex visualised using Biovia Discovery Studio, version 2025, and B) represents the 3D image of the ZNO-CAC1C complex visualised using PyMol, 3.1

The ligand-protein complex of ZNO-CALBI (Figure 12) had a binding energy score of -5.1kcal/mol. Conventional H-bonding with SER (A: 257), carbon-hydrogen bonding with SER (A:

257), and pi-alkyl interactions with the alkyl group of ALA (A: 253) and pi-electron cloud of the aromatic ring of ZNO secures the stability of the complex.

Figure 12: a) represents the 2D image of the ZNO-CALB1 complex visualised using Biovia Discovery Studio, version 2025, and B) represents the 3D image of the ZNO-CALB1 complex visualised using PyMol, 3.1

The ZNO-CREB1 (Figure 13) complex has a binding energy score of -4.7kcal/mol. The stability of the complex is reinforced by pi-pi stacking between TYR (A: 168) and the aromatic ring of

ZNO. Further conventional H-bonds with ALA (A: 180) and pi-alkyl interactions with ILE (A: 160) secured the stability of the complex.

Figure 13: a) represents the 2D image of the ZNO-CREB1 complex visualised using Biovia Discovery Studio, version 2025, and b) represents the 3D image of the ZNO-CREB1 complex visualised using PyMol, 3.1

Molecular dynamics analysis of ligand-protein complex

On molecular docking analysis, KCC2A and KCC4 were found to have the highest binding energy with ZNO and were therefore considered for molecular dynamics simulation analysis.

The ligand-protein complex of ZNO-KCC2A (Figure 14) was analysed, and the RMSD was run for 100ns. The RMSD graph (Figure 14a) indicated that the ZNO-KCC2A complex reached a state of structural stability after 30ns, with the RMSD of the complex stabilising at 1.1nm and the KCC2A backbone at 0.9nm. ZNO was shown to be stable with minuscule fluctuations and an RMSD value of less than 2.0nm during the simulation run, indicating a strong and stable binding with the active site of KCC2A. The results indicated that both ZNO and KCC2A are structurally stable and an intact ZNO-KCC2A complex during the entire run of the simulation, which further validates the binding interactions.

The RMSF plot (Figure 14b) indicated the flexibility of amino acid residues during the

simulation. The majority of the residues showed low fluctuations, typically less than 0.5nm, indicative of overall rigidity. However, some of the peaks, particularly around residues 320 and 420, indicated higher flexibility, which may correspond to loop regions or surface-exposed regions. The N-terminal region also indicated higher fluctuations, which may be expected due to its exposed and less structured nature. The overall results indicated that KCC2A had a stable core with restricted flexibility in some regions, which could be of functional significance.

The Rg plot (Figure 14c) indicated the overall compactness and structural integrity of KCC2A during the 100ns simulation. The overall Rg (black line) showed relative stability around 2.6nm, indicating that KCC2A remained compact without any unfolding or collapse. The Rg values along individual axes (green, blue, red) indicated fewer fluctuations, particularly in the X and Z directions, indicating minor conformational adjustments. However, the uniformity in the overall Rg plot ensured that KCC2A maintained its overall structural integrity and did not undergo significant conformational changes during the simulation.

The SASA plot (Figure 14d) of ZNO-KCC2A showed initial high levels $\sim 265\text{nm}^2$, which implied a more extended or a less compact conformation. With the progression of time, the SASA casually decreased and stabilised around 240nm^2 , indicative of compactness and stability in the complex. The decrease in SASA was an indication that KCC2A preferred to minimise the exposed surface area, possibly due to favourable folding or tighter packaging, leading to overall structural stability of the solvated form.

The H-bond analysis (Figure 14e) showed that 1 to 3 H-bonds were maintained constantly between ZNO and KCC2A throughout the 100ns simulation, with occasional spikes to 5 H-bonds. The constant number of H-bonds and close interacting atom pairs within 0.35nm can be an indication of a stable and favourable interaction between ZNO and KCC2A binding site. The dynamic and stable H-bonding indicated that ZNO was well-anchored and contributed to the overall binding stability throughout the simulation.

Figure 14: Molecular dynamics simulation trajectories of ZNO-KCC2A complex run for 100ns. a) RMSD plot of ZNO-KCC2A complex. b) RMS fluctuation plot of ZNO-KCC2A complex. c) Rg plot of ZNO-KCC2A complex. d) SASA plot of ZNO-KCC2A complex and e) H-bonding plot of ZNO-KCC2A complex

The binding energy analysis showed that the total binding free energy of the ZNO-KCC2A complex was around $-78.03 \pm 10.72\text{kJ/mol}$, which specifies a favourable and stable interaction. The van der Waals energy was the greatest contributor with a value of $-127.20 \pm 8.79\text{kJ/mol}$, indicative of strong hydrophobic interactions. The electrostatic energy also contributed with $-17.08 \pm 4.90\text{kJ/mol}$, whereas the polar solvation energy was positive with a value of $79.64 \pm 6.78\text{kJ/mol}$. The SASA energy

contributed moderately ($-13.39 \pm 0.56\text{kJ/mol}$), which implied the role of minor contributions from the solvent-accessibility surface. In general, the negative binding energy verified an energetically favourable and stable ZNO-KCC2A complex formation.

The ligand-protein complex of ZNO-KCC4 (Figure 15) was analysed, and the RMSD plot (Figure 15a) showed ZNO-KCC4 complex was structurally stable during the 100ns

simulation. The RMSD of the complex (black line) intensified in the initial 40ns and then fluctuated between 0.4nm and 0.5nm subsequently. This may be indicative of conformational flexibility of the complex. The RMSD of KCC4 (red line) was shown to be stable at 0.3nm, signifying a well-preserved protein backbone. The RMSD of ZNO (green line) had lessened fluctuations at 0.2nm throughout the simulation, which may reveal that ZNO was securely bound to the active site of KCC4 without much movement.

In the RMSF plot of ZNO-KCC4 (Figure 15b), the majority of residues showed low fluctuation of less than 0.3nm, which may have indicated that KCC4 was stable and had a rigid structure. Higher peaks at residues 190 and 270 showed patches of high flexibility, which presumably corresponded to loop regions or surface-exposed regions. The C-terminal end around residue 340 showed the highest fluctuation, about 1.0nm, as anticipated, probably due to solvent exposure and lack of secondary structural restraints. The results indicated a stable KCC4 core with flexible terminal and loop regions.

The Rg plot (Figure 15c) showed the overall protein compactness. The ZNO-KCC2A complex was stable throughout the 100ns simulation. The total Rg (black line) fluctuated slightly around 2.0nm, which specified that the protein had a consistent and compact structure without any significant unfolding or expansion. The Rg values along the individual

axes showed minor variations, with the blue line showing slightly larger variation, reflecting small-scale conformational flexibility along the axis. The overall Rg plot reflected that the overall protein structure was well-conserved during the simulation.

The SASA (Figure 15d) plot showed the variation of the exposed surface area of KCC4 during the course of the 100ns simulation. SASA fluctuated around an average of $\sim 157\text{nm}^2$, reflecting that the protein had significantly maintained its relative stability and compactness with minimal conformational variations. No significant fluctuations were observed, which reflected the absence of large-scale unfolding or collapse. These stable values signified that the protein maintained its integrity and structural compactness in the solvated environment during the course of the 100ns simulation.

The H-bond analysis (Figure 15e) revealed that the ZNO-KCC4 complex showed 1 to 3 H-bonds occasionally during the course of the 100ns simulation, with occasional peaks, up to 5 contacts in 035ns. Although the number of H-bonds decreased after 20ns, some interactions were sustained, indicative of repetitive but transient contacts between KCC4 and ZNO. The fluctuation pattern reflected strong and persistent H-bonds may be rare, however, short-range interactions were sustained. This may be probably due to dynamic but stable binding mode during the 100ns simulation.

Figure 15: Molecular dynamics simulation trajectories of ZNO-KCC4 complex run for 100ns. a) RMSD plot of ZNO-KCC2A complex. b) RMS fluctuation plot of ZNO-KCC4 complex, c) Rg plot of ZNO-KCC4 complex. d) SASA plot of ZNO-KCC4 complex and e) H-bonding plot of ZNO-KCC4 complex

The binding energy analysis revealed a total binding free energy of -32.54 ± 10.20 kJ/mol, which reflected a moderately stable and favourable interaction between ZNO and KCC4. The van der Waals energy of -49.91 ± 11.46 kJ/mol indicated that hydrophobic interactions were the most significant contributory factor, reflecting their primary role in ZNO-KCC4 stabilisation. The electrostatic interactions (-8.24 ± 5.30 kJ/mol) contributed positively towards the stability of ZNO and KCC4, while the polar solvation energy resisted binding with a positive contribution (32.38 ± 8.27 kJ/mol), as expected due to desolvation costs. The SASA energy score -6.76 ± 1.13 kJ/mol indicated a diminutive contribution from the buried surface area. The overall negative binding energy specified a stable ZNO-KCC4 complex, sustained mainly by van der Waals and electrostatic contributions.

DISCUSSION

Ca²⁺ signalling has been of notable interest in ASD pathology. Ca²⁺ has a prominent role in synaptogenesis and synaptic transmission, signifying diversified roles in synaptic plasticity^[37]. Timothy syndrome, associated with autistic features due to de novo mutations in the Ca²⁺ voltage-gated ion channel *CACNAC1C* gene, fragile X syndrome, and tuberous sclerosis, associated with inositol trisphosphate-mediated Ca²⁺ signalling, indicating a convergent role of Ca²⁺ signalling in autistic patients^[38]. The PVALB hypothesis related to Ca²⁺ signalling has been described in the autistic postmortem brain. Filice et al. (2020)^[39] have hypothesised that PVALB downregulation, affecting the electrical properties of the PVALB-expressing neurons and pyramidal cells, can be a contributing factor towards the aetiology of ASD; however, it may be of restricted interest, as the no. of cases expressing valuable mutations in favour of the hypothesis is limited in autistic patients. Another study found that the immature formation of the dentate gyrus (iDG) in

the forebrain of mice was due to downregulation of calcineurin, accompanied by downregulated calbindin, calretinin, and phosphorylated cAMP response element binding protein. These findings were also reflective of clinical autistic patients with iDG leading to neuropsychiatric disorders, and downregulation of the CNB1 subunit of calcineurin in the cortex of human patients with ASD^[40]. CAMKIV, a core constituent in Ca²⁺ signalling, is associated with neuronal differentiation and mitochondrial energy generation. Missense (p. Gly228Arg), splice site (1101G > A), and copy number variant duplication (5:g. (110,260,870–110,730,612) duplication; (91,562,441–111,573,636) duplication) have been linked to ASD and intellectual disability, highlighting the role of Ca²⁺ signalling proteins^[6]. Lower BDNF levels in blood serum were correlated with autistic core symptoms such as social communication defects and restricted behaviours. Downregulated BDNF levels in ASD individuals were associated with dendritic and axonal anomalies^[7].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, for the first time, we report through in silico analysis, the Ca²⁺ signalling proteins that were considered as potential pathways associated with ASD in clinical studies have been studied against ZNO to understand its binding affinity and ligand-protein complex stability. The strong binding affinity of ZNO with Ca²⁺ signalling proteins may indicate the possible involvement of ZNO in mitigating the ASD like phenotypes in vivo through the Ca²⁺ signalling pathway. However, the regulatory/modulatory/inhibitory activity of ZNO against Ca²⁺ proteins and their related genes needs to be further assessed using molecular techniques in rodent models to confirm the role of ZNO in neuroprotection against ASD-like symptoms.

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